

ReNEW

D3.6 Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application v1

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
ABS	Agent-Based Simulation
AIS	Automatic Identification System
BN	Bayesian Network
BPM	Business Process Modeling
CEMT	European Conference of Ministers of Transport
CPT	Conditional Probability Tables
DE	Discrete Events
DINA	Digital Inland Navigation
DT	Digital Twin
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
GA	Grant Agreement
GPICS	Generic PI Case Study
ICONET	New ICT infrastructure and reference architecture to support Operations in future PI Logistics NETWORKS
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
ID	Influence Diagrams
IoT	Internet of Things
IW-NET	Innovation-driven Collaborative European Inland Waterways Transport Network
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LL(s)	Living Lab(s)
OLDT(s)	Open Local Digital Twin(s)
PoC	Proof of Concept
PI	Physical Internet
SP	Shore Power
SD	System Dynamics
ToC	Table of Content
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UC(s)	Use Case(s)
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive Summary

This document contains the first version description of the Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application, with its primary focus being the identification and description of models and tools that will compose the Digital Twin.

A diverse collection of models and tools has been compiled from project partners. These models span various maturity levels and technologies, including multi-agent systems, discrete events, bayesian networks, knowledge graphs, and dynamic routing models. They form the initial foundation of the project's modeling and simulation capabilities, addressing a wide range of applications. This encompasses the evaluation of inland waterway transport resilience and sustainability and facilitates the prediction of impact and cascading effects related to hazard and vulnerability scenarios, among other utilities. In addition, insights from simulation libraries of previous projects like IW-NET and ICONET have been incorporated, enhancing the design of models for the assessment of Inland Waterway Transport resilience and sustainability.

Data availability is essential for the Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application. The project team has introduced Data Spaces to enable seamless data integration. This document outlines the requirements for information sharing, data space interactions, and the integration of various data sources.

A methodology for identifying key performance indicators that evaluate inland waterway transport resilience and sustainability is described. A comprehensive list of relevant indicators is provided to align with the Living Labs' requirements.

The document also presents a methodology for capturing Living Labs' needs and aligning them with practical Digital Twin use cases. As a proof of concept, it outlines potential applications of these models within each Living Lab. Ongoing model evolution, potential new additions, and refinements are expected as they integrate data and user/stakeholder feedback in the coming months. This document serves as a comprehensive record of these crucial advancements.

2 Introduction

2.1 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The following table (Table 1) maps the ReNEW’s Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work to perform.

Table 1. Adherence to ReNEW’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

Deliverable D3.6 (Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application v1)		
Report on metrics and KPIs for the LL use cases using DT, Data Spaces, and ReNEW services and Solutions Deployed; Simulation Libraries, Simulated models at the level of Proof of Concept.		
Task 3.3 (Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application)		
Apply the Data Spaces and Digital Twins approach, ensuring that coherent and complementary data are available in the LLs to support the Decision Process and the sustainability and resilience strategies and initiatives. Create a comprehensive set of KPIs and Metrics and introduce driven by the LL needs realistic simulation scenarios for sustainable and resilient IWT infrastructures and transportation resources.		
ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST3.3.1 (LL Digital Twins for Decision Making, Metrics and KPIs evaluation)	Select the appropriate ecological, human, and technical indicators to empower the recommendations for resilient and sustainable actions that can be deployed with a long-term systemic benefit. Using the WP1 Resilience and Sustainability methodology, collect a list of non-functional features to be considered in the decision process of each LL creating the assessment baselines. Based on the user story maps, identify the relevant data sets, integrate, and provide access to necessary external data sets via the Data Spaces, and create a plan for the smooth integration the DTs into the decisionmaking process to evaluate and simulate different type of actions (encompassing physical, digital, and functional innovations). Each LL action shall be assessed with one or several performance indicators (WP1) and depending on the use case the DT will be	<p>In Chapter 4, the characteristics to be considered in the assessment of IWT resilience and sustainability at various scales are described, and the necessary indicators for evaluating resilient and sustainable actions, specifically for each LL, are selected.</p> <p>Chapter 6 covers the requirements for sharing information with Data Spaces, the definition of interactions with the Digital Twin, and the integration of data.</p> <p>In Chapter 7, a methodology for applying the Digital Twin to LLs is described.</p>

	<p>computing the relevant KPIs. Evaluation scenarios shall be selected and conducted based on available historical data and benchmarks. Per relevant LL use case produce the set of calibrated metrics for the IWT system states and performance evaluation, facilitating that the Digital Twins will properly consider the LL measures initial or current states, and will compute the resulting metrics for resilient and sustainable actions.</p>	
<p>ST3.3.2 (Libraries and Tools for DT enabled dynamic simulation models)</p>	<p>Provide the tools and solution libraries to design, evaluate, and implement policies, as well as to understand their impact by real-time predictive simulations. Create a modelling and simulation capability for generating substantive model abstractions that simplify the reasoning process for IWT modal shift models, amendable to synthesis techniques for investigating impact of IWT resilience. Create a cloud-based open simulation framework that integrates, synchronizes and orchestrates several simulation models (e.g., discrete events, multiagent) from third parties as well as innovative and advanced visualization and interaction technologies to interact with the simulations. Use IW-NET and ICONET developed libraries and develop and extend a set of libraries specifically targeted to Resilience and Sustainability scenarios to simulate, assess and to source evidence-based decisions at the strategic, tactical and operations levels, dealing with climate crisis related events. Based on the user stories, create models with the capability to represent the behaviour of real transport elements in the digital twin with the support for integration with other digital services.</p>	<p>Chapter 5 provides a description of the various models that comprise the project’s modeling and simulation capability. Additionally, it conducts a review of the libraries developed within the IW-NET and ICONET projects.</p>

2.2 Deliverable Structure

In this section, we outline the structure of our report, which includes chapters focused on exploring the state of IWT and the Digital Twin, assessing IWT capabilities, and defining the architecture of the Digital Twin.

In Chapter 3, we offer a thorough exploration of the current state of the art in the context of Inland Water Transport and Digital Twins. This encompasses a literature review, an analysis of current technological advancements, recent developments in the field, and relevant case studies.

Chapter 4 describes the characteristics essential for evaluating IWT capabilities. Utilizing the Resilience and Sustainability methodology from WP1, we compile the appropriate indicators (resilience, environmental, and economic) to guide the decision-making process for each Living Lab.

In Chapter 5, we outline the general architecture of the Digital Twin. It provides detailed descriptions of the models identified within WP1 and WP3 that could potentially serve as components of the Digital Twin. Additionally, this chapter reviews libraries developed in prior projects (IW-NET, ICONET) that can serve as references for adaptation and evolution throughout the project.

Chapter 6 introduces the concept of Data Spaces and elucidates their importance in the context of the Digital Twin. We delve into details like the requirements for information sharing, interactions between the data space and the Digital Twin, and the integration of static, historical, and real-time data.

In Chapter 7, we provide a detailed account of the methodology used to identify the needs of the Living Labs, subsequently mapping them into use cases that the Digital Twin should address. Additionally, in this chapter, we describe the iterative development methodology for the models comprising the Digital Twin, offering insight into the potential applications of these models within each Living Lab.

In Chapter 8, we offer comprehensive conclusions and recommendations to pave the way toward the final version of the Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application.

3 Framework

3.1 Literature Review

3.1.1 Urban Freight Transport

Urban freight transport is a linchpin for sustaining the urban economy and improving the quality of life) (Browne & Allen, 2011). At the same time, however, it is associated with significant externalities, including energy consumption and emissions (Vurdelja & Vogrin, 2005). While numerous solutions have been proposed and implemented by urban authorities to improve urban transportation systems, most of these measures have focused on the mobility of people and often neglected the pressing challenges associated with urban freight transport (Goetz, 2010).

In most cities, urban freight transport relies primarily on road infrastructure, while rail and waterways are rarely used to transport goods within urban areas (Behrends, 2012). Despite the increasing recognition of alternative modes of transport, such as waterways, some authors recognize the potential to shift some intra-urban freight flows to more sustainable waterway networks (Commission staff, 2021; UNECE NEXUS, 2021). Inland waterways, characterized by ample capacity and minimal congestion, emerge as a compelling alternative. Its inherent energy efficiency and lower carbon footprint compared to trains and trucks make it economically competitive (Durajczyk & Drop, 2021).

Despite these challenges, some cities successfully use inland waterways for urban freight. These cities include (Pauwels et al., 2021):

- Amsterdam, Netherlands.
- Antwerp, Belgium.
- Brussels, Belgium.
- Paris, France.
- London, UK.

A growing market share for intermodal transport should mean a shift towards more environmentally friendly transport modes, less congestion, and better accessibility and opening-up of the seaports. Using IWT in urban areas is also desirable from an environmental perspective. Van Lier & Macharis, (2011) calculated substantial benefits in terms of external transport costs saved by using the inland port of Brussels, where some 255,000 truck trips going in or out of the city are avoided every year due to inland waterway transport, mainly in the bulk product categories minerals, building materials and petroleum products, but also in food products and containers. Promoting IWT is a long-term priority to achieve a sustainable European transport system. Currently, inland waterway transport is important in the hinterland connectivity of significant Western European seaports.

However, it's crucial to recognize that the role of IWT extends beyond urban logistics. Inland waterways are traditionally significant for transporting dry bulk, chemicals, and other goods in various

regions. These sectors represent a substantial portion of the market for IWT and are critical for its economic viability and environmental impact.

3.1.2 Dry Bulk Transport

Enhancements in transportation networks make it more cost-effective to ship goods, especially large volumes of low-cost bulk items, over greater distances. Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) has traditionally been seen as a straightforward method for transporting large quantities of bulk goods. While this still holds true for many bulk commodities, the dynamics change with containerized shipping. In the realm of container shipping, IWT is increasingly becoming an integral part of the supply chain, even taking on roles in supply chain coordination.

Figure 2 presents a sub-model of a discrete-event simulation that starts with the intake of various commodities. These commodities are organized into four primary groups:

- Dry cargo, encompassing items like iron, steel, and manufacturing equipment or machinery.
- Dry bulk cargo, which includes materials such as chemical fertilizers, coal and coke, sand/gravel and rock, minerals, and building materials.
- Liquid bulk cargo, consisting of a range of other chemicals and petroleum products.
- Grains, which cover agricultural products like wheat, soybeans, and other food or farm-related goods.

This categorization is crucial for managing and simulating the flow and handling of different types of goods in the simulation (Oztanriseven & Nachtmann, 2020).

Figure 1. Changes in port calls per half year, world total First semester 2019–second semester 2021 (year-on-year differences).

Figure 2. Origin ports and discrete-event simulation sub-processes.

Also, the study of (Wienk, 2021) focuses on dry-bulk transport from Rotterdam to Duisburg and liquid-bulk transport from Rotterdam to Wesseling. The objective is for IWT to perform better than railway transport during periods of low flow. Five performance indicators are used to assess the system state: number of trips, transported cargo, transportation costs, transportation costs per ton, and transportation costs per ton kilometer. A simulation model is set up to identify tipping points according to the performance indicators. The model concept is based on the OpenCLSim software package. The stress test consists of multiple simulations in which the low water period duration builds up over the simulations and the water depth is kept constant during the low flow period. Three stress tests are performed with different water depth scenarios. The results show that the duration of a low flow period IWT can cope with depends on the water depth scenario. For the most severe water depth scenario, the maximum duration of a low flow period IWT can cope with is 10 weeks.

3.1.3 Digital Twin Review in Waterway Transport

Recent experiments in urban logistics have demonstrated the competitiveness of inland navigation not only for the long-distance transport of bulk goods but also for the transport of goods on a smaller scale within dense urban areas. However, little literature addresses the intermodal opportunities of urban logistics, and even fewer studies focus on initiatives that utilize the inland waterway network. Diziain et al., (2014) address urban logistics solutions implemented in France and Japan using rail and waterway networks. Maes et al., (2015) analyze different water-based urban distribution schemes in the Netherlands and evaluate their applicability in the Flanders region.

With the development of the smart city, technologies such as the Internet of Things, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and digital twins have been widely applied in all aspects of life. DTs technology is at the heart of realizing Cyber-Physical Systems. It leverages data, integrates multi-disciplinary, multi-physical, multi-scale, and multi-probability simulation processes, completes the mapping in virtual space, and reflects the entire lifecycle process of the corresponding physical equipment. DTs technology provides new ideas for vehicle development, intelligent infrastructure operation and maintenance, virtual unmanned driving tests, and live traffic analysis. It effectively solves complex urban traffic congestion and slow traffic operations (Wu et al., 2022).

The literature review examines different definitions and interpretations of the term "Digital Twin" (DT) and highlights its evolution and diverse applications. By providing a digital identity, synchronized visualization, and virtual and actual interaction, the DT can potentially enhance the transportation industry. NASA introduced the concept of DT as an integrated probabilistic simulation of vehicles or systems that incorporates physical models, sensor data, and fleet history to mirror the real-world counterpart (Shafto et al., 2012). However, later authors have provided different definitions.

Boschert & Rosen, (2016) view DT as an evolving description of a component, product, or system about its real-world counterpart. Grieves & Vickers, (2017) define it as a comprehensive set of virtual information constructs covering a physical product's micro to macro level. Zheng et al., (2019) describe it as an integrated system capable of simulating, monitoring, computing, regulating, and controlling the status and processes of the system.

Several practical applications of DTs are discussed in the literature. Brenner & Hummel, (2017) developed a digital store floor management system based on the concept of DT. Knapp et al., (2017) used a three-dimensional DT to predict variables affecting metallurgical structures, although no direct sensor connections existed. Schleich et al., (2017) proposed a reference model for DT in product design and manufacturing. Alam and El Saddik (2017) used DTs in a driver assistance application. (Uhlemann et al., 2017) presented a learning factory based on DTs. Finally, (Zheng et al., 2019) used DTs to model a welding production line.

Ambra & Macharis, (2020) framework for Agent-Based Digital Twins (ABM-DTs) in Synchronodal Transport and Logistics are presented in addition to these earlier studies in their publication from 2022. Road, rail, and inland waterways are all included in synchronodal transportation. The ABM-DT framework enables the testing of transportation hypotheses by creating a virtual simulation of the complete synchronodal transport network. It optimizes the movement of commodities for increased sustainability and efficiency. Also, the review paper from Ali et al., (2022) focuses on Digital Twin technology in intelligent transportation, particularly in electric mobility and autonomous vehicles. It explores its integration with the Internet of Things and 5G to address critical issues in electric vehicle services.

3.2 Current State of Technology

Digitalization is rapidly expanding into all areas of society, and the inland waterway transport (IWT) sector is no exception. IWT experts should look to existing digital solutions for inspiration, as reusing and building on existing systems can significantly shorten the time to market and avoid duplication of effort and investment.

Finland is a leader in IWT digitalization and automation, but even there, there are challenges, such as the age of the vessels. Older vessels may not have the technology required to take advantage of the latest digital solutions. However, Finland is integrating digitalization into its channel markings and remote monitoring and management systems. Remote pilotage is a promising technology that could improve the safety and efficiency of shipping.

Automated mooring and cargo handling can save time and allow for transshipments to happen at any time, regardless of the port's operating hours. A digital twin is a virtual copy of a ship that allows customers and shipowners to track its status and predict its arrival time (Sari & Patrick, 2022). In the following we have the summary of the European project INFUTUR (Lybeck, 2019).

Finland is at the forefront of developing and implementing remote pilotage solutions:

- Cargo vessels have 30–40 separate technical systems in their engine room. All those systems should be made fully automatic, redundant, and possibly duplicated.
- Automation providers have started to explore the integration of these systems.
- On 17 January 2019, the Government of Finland decided to amend the Pilotage Act to allow remote pilotage subject to authorisation.
- Investments required in the ships for remote pilotage should remain modest.
- Remote control has been tested earlier in, for example, Norway and Denmark.
- In Finland, pilotage has been digitised by adopting a mobile ERP system for real-time monitoring of the pilotage performance.

In this way European commission publish a strategic document. The Digital Inland Navigation (DINA) Vision 2030 is a strategic document that outlines the future of inland navigation in Europe. It was developed by the European Commission and the European Parliament in 2019. DINA Vision 2030 sets out a number of specific objectives:

- Optimize traffic and route planning.
- Provide real-time and predicted traffic information to support voyage planning.
- Make waterway transport visible in digital supply chain.
- Optimize berth management.

The Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy aims to reduce transport sector emissions by 90% by 2050. Digitalisation is crucial for modernizing the transport system, improving safety, security, reliability, and comfort. The NAIADES III Communication aims to make inland waterway transport

smarter by advancing digitalization. This will improve governance competitiveness, integration into multimodal chains, and reduce administrative burdens. The Commission will facilitate digitalization and automation, with input from Digital Inland Navigation Area, NAIADES, and Digital Transport and Logistics Forum Expert Groups. By 2035, European waterway infrastructure will be highly automated and remotely controlled, with smart infrastructure management and safe coexistence of automated and conventional vessels (sensors, digital twins, prediction tools, etc.) (Digital Inland Waterway Area, DINA Expert Group and the members of the NAIADES Expert Group.).

3.3 Recent Advances and Developments

IWT is a sustainable transport mode that helps achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving air quality, and creating jobs (Barros et al., 2022). Their paper shows increased interest in eco-friendly practices for IWT, such as using renewable energy and reducing pollution. However, social issues, such as the impact of IWT on local communities, remain underappreciated. Also, IWT is facing climate-related disruptions, such as more frequent and severe changes in water level. Inland barge companies can build resilience to these disruptions by using technological systems, good customer service, collaboration, and strong knowledge and experience in the industry.

Governments can also play an important role by maintaining and strengthening infrastructure for waterway transportation (Ahlgren & Jamac, 2023). Aritua et al., (2021) technological innovation, multimodal connectivity, and smart shipping will expand IWT's role and influence. International cooperation and standardization will help other countries benefit from China's experiences, such as the Working with Nature concept. (Wang et al., 2023) were working in covid-pandemic period. In the post-pandemic era, a flexible freight consolidation strategy is proposed to guide cargos to be concentrated among the ports via a multi-modal transportation system. The proposed strategy can be formulated as a non-linear mathematical programming model and discretized to a 0–1 Knapsack problem by the finite element method and calculated with branch-and-bound algorithm. The Yangtze River Economic Belt is adopted to illustrate the validity of the proposed strategy and algorithm. Another European project that is named AEGIS (The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research innovation program under Grant Agreement N°859992) is a three-year project (started in June 2020) that aims to develop a new waterborne transport system for Europe that is more efficient, sustainable, and user-friendly. The project focused on automating ships, ports, and administrative tasks, and on developing new ship types and multimodal logistics solutions. The goal was to make waterborne transport more attractive and competitive, and to help Europe achieve its goal of transferring more than 50% of road transport to rail or waterways by 2050 (Krause et al., 2022).

The following is a compilation of case studies from real-world implementations of IWT resilience strategies and digital twin applications. These are successful projects that have effectively addressed challenges related to climate events, resilience and sustainable transportation, and from which we

can draw valuable lessons and insights to guide our own project approach and decision-making process.

Case study: Digital Twin for Inland Waterways

Project name: PortForward (2018, for 42 months) (Grant agreement ID: 769267)

Objective: To develop a digital twin platform for IWT that could be used to improve the efficiency, safety, and sustainability of IWT operations. The PortForward project developed a digital twin platform for IWT that integrated data from a variety of sources, including:

- Vessel data (e.g., position, speed, cargo).
- Infrastructure data (e.g., locks, bridges, canals).
- Meteorological and hydrological data (e.g., wind, waves, currents).
- Traffic data.

The digital twin platform is used to simulate and predict IWT operations in real time. This enables users to:

- Identify and optimize vessel routes and schedules.
- Improve traffic management.
- Reduce fuel consumption and emissions.
- Enhance safety.

The PortForward digital twin platform was being developed and tested in three pilot areas:

- The Port of Antwerp in Belgium.
- The Port of Rotterdam in the Netherlands.
- The Rhine River in Germany.

Case study: Digital Twin for Inland Waterways

Project name: RiverTwin (2004-2007) (ID Finanzhilfvereinbarung: 505401)

Objective: To develop and demonstrate a digital twin platform for IWT that could be used to improve the efficiency, safety, and sustainability of IWT operations, while also supporting the integration of IWT into multimodal transportation networks. The RiverTwin project developed a digital twin platform for IWT that integrated data from a variety of sources, including:

- Vessel data (e.g., position, speed, cargo).
- Infrastructure data (e.g., locks, bridges, canals).
- Meteorological and hydrological data (e.g., wind, waves, currents).
- Traffic data.

- Socio-economic data (e.g., demand for IWT services).

The digital twin platform was used to simulate and predict IWT operations under different scenarios, including:

- Different vessel types and sizes.
- Different traffic conditions.
- Different weather conditions.
- Different infrastructure conditions.

The RiverTwin digital twin platform was used to support a number of real-world applications, including:

- Optimizing vessel routes in the Danube River.
- Improving traffic management in the Rhine River.
- Predicting and mitigating the impact of low water levels on the Seine River.
- Assessing the environmental impact of different IWT scenarios in the Ebro River Delta.

The RiverTwin project was a good example of how European Union funding could be used to develop and deploy innovative digital technologies that had a real impact on the economy, society, and the environment.

4 Metrics and KPIs

Based on the WP1 Resilience and Sustainability methodology, D1.8 (Tami et al., 2023) and the Living Labs needs in term of these two aspects, a list of KPI has been established in order to evaluate the IWT capabilities. These indicators and KPIs allow the characterization and the assessment of the IWT resilience and sustainability at different scales and also in short term and in the long-term purposes. In addition, KPIs could be measured on the resilient system at different phases before or after a climate change-based event, namely, withstanding, absorptive, restorative phases. Each of these indicators focuses on different perspectives encompassing resilience and sustainability:

- **Reliability:** Can be defined as the degree to which deliveries arrive on time, i.e., the percentage of shipments arriving on time in a certain time period (month, year). It is expected that low and high-water levels in waterways will result in an increase in the number of inland waterway deliveries that do not arrive on time.
- **Robustness:** Represents the minimum level of service achieved during the disruption scenario, in other words, it represents the withstand capacity of the IWT system to face the stress without degradation of service.
- **Sensitivity:** It represents the capacity to detect the event or factor affecting the IWT system and translate it to KPI variation.
- **Selectivity:** The selectivity depicts the capacity to detect a change in the properties of the IWT system, localize it and isolate it. In other words, it is the ability to discriminate an effect.
- **Scalability:** It represents the ability to extend operating capacity and handle growing activities and demand.
- **Adaptability:** The adaptability describes the ability to analyse acceptable options, identify alternatives and elaborate a plan.
- **Flexibility:** The ability to take swift action in response to unforeseen events. It's an agility capability among other capabilities such as responsiveness.
- **Agility:** It represents the ability IWT system to respond quickly to changes in order to mitigate its impact if necessary.
- **Rapidity:** It represents the quickness with which the system recovers after disturbance.
- **Resourcefulness:** It represents the capacity to identify weaknesses, and mobilize resources (financial, human, technological).
- **Protectiveness:** It depicts the capacity of constituents and infrastructures to protect from the unforeseen events and worst scenarios.

Within the methodology, a well-defined process is established for calculating and measuring these KPIs (Table 2), complete with the specification of their corresponding units, measurement methods, and data sources. These KPIs are systematically grouped according to the perspectives described above. Furthermore, connections are drawn between these KPIs for each Living Lab, with an emphasis on those that are shared among LLs and those that are unique to each.

Table 2. WP1 methodology for the collection of KPI information. Source: ReNEW D1.8.

KPI name	Full name of the KPI
Category	Category to which the indicator belongs (resilience or sustainability).
Sub-Category	The sub-category of belonging.
Acronym	Term used to assign the KPI or the indicator.
Type	Indicate the type of the data: Real, Boolean, String...
Unit	Indicates the measurement unit, percentage, no unit...
Description	Description of the KPI/ measure/ indicator.
Objective	Describes the expected purposes through this indicator or its added value.
Measurement method	Describe the formula enabling the calculation of the indicator or how to acquire the measure whether is directedly provided by sensors or systems.
Frequency	Represents the number of samples per period, or the number of refreshes per time period.
Safe limit	The operating limit may be considered as the nominal interval in which the system should ideally operate. However, the safe limits for each entity in the IWT must be defined later. At a safe limit, there is not yet an emergency situation, but it implies actions to bring the behaviour back into the nominal range. Beyond the safe limits, there are emergency limits. If the measurement rises over emergency limits, an immediate action is required.
Reporting format	Describes how to display the information through chart, text...
Sources	Sources providing the data to calculate the indicator.

A list of 130 metrics has been defined in ReNEW’s deliverable D1.1 (Jović & Duhme, 2023), from this list and after several workshops and deals with the partners, AKKODIS narrowed it down to select the most relevant metrics for each LL (95 metrics). 68 metrics are common, 5 are specific to LL1, 15 are specific to LL2, 6 are specific to LL3 and one is specific to LL4. These metrics help us to determine datasets and KPIs to reach resilience and sustainability achievement in different sessions with the stakeholders. The synthesis has been done on deliverable D3.8 (Azzi et al., 2023a).

To proceed with the identification of LLs’ KPIs and datasets, AKKODIS started from the generic list of Resilience and Sustainability Key Performance Indicators (KPI) provided by our partner ISL from WP1 in deliverable D1.1.

Starting from the generic KPI list and with the help of partners AKKODIS narrowed the list down by selecting the KPIs that AKKODIS deemed relevant for the Digital Twin, considering each LL and the project objectives. Then AKKODIS crossed the selection between WP3 and WP1 to embed all the relevant KPIs also considering this time all our partners’ objectives. Considering resilience and sustainability commitments, all partners engaged in workshops with the different LLs, to refine, clarify and finally validate each metric.

During this phase, it has been determined whether the datasets required were available. When the identification phase was over and with help of IMEC, partners then organized workshops with each

LLs to classify the sets of use cases and KPIs. To do so AKKODIS decided to devise a ranking system based on the prioritization of the validated lists.

In conclusion from 130 metrics, 68 have been selected as common, 34 KPIs and 34 datasets. We agreed in D3.8 (Azzi et al., 2023b) that if at least two LLs share a metric, the metric will be considered common for all and with the highest LL level priority.

Twelve metrics are mentioned as an undefined priority, we are waiting for more inputs from LLs. 25 metrics are shared by all LLs, 19 metrics by three LLs and finally, 24 metrics are shared by two LLs. Only 3 metrics considered as datasets are available for all LLs, they concern water level, fairway status, and bridge clearance.

The common sustainability metrics selected, other than those defined in the Great Agreement, are basically the environmental and economic KPIs and datasets. One social dataset has been selected, it concerns thresholds of pollution, and the data must be defined for LL1 and LL2 later, some conclusions from the LLs are underway. These sustainability metrics may help us by providing services in a responsible manner and refers to the ability to maintain the quality and reproducibility of natural resources.

The common resilience metrics selected are distributed as follows: 20 datasets distributed on all resilience scope, and 18 KPIs focused on risk management, flexibility and agility, rapidity, resourcefulness and collaboration. These resilience metrics may help us by resourcefulness supply chain to avoid and anticipate some risks to implement mitigation strategies,

- The ability to respond to quick changes.
- Deployment of solution within agreed period.
- Capacity to identify problems and establish priorities.
- The ability to respond to supply chain disruptions with partners through collaborative planning and information to coordinate the immediate response.

Common metric summary is on D3.8 Annexes, while specific metrics are detailed in dedicated sections.

4.1 Resilience and Environmental Metrics and KPIs

To assess the resilience of the IWT, we will identify and quantify various metrics and KPIs that directly relate to its ability to withstand disruptions, recover from adverse events, and maintain sustainable practices.

Considering the “Reduce environmental impact” resilience KPI defined in the GA, some 28 metrics related to environmental aspects have been selected, they all relate to sustainability.

Table 3. List of Resilience and Environmental Metrics and KPIs.

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level
Sustainability			
Environmental			
#01	Total direct or indirect emissions of greenhouse gases by weight	KPI	2-High priority
#02	Reduced CO2 emissions per fleet	KPI	2-High priority
#03	Renewable sources rate	KPI	4-Low priority (Specific to LL1)
#04	Waste reduction rate	KPI	1-Very high priority (Specific to LL2)
#05	Efficiency resources use rate	KPI	2-High priority (Specific to LL3)
#06	Reduced fuel energy (IW-NET project) Defined as Reduced energy consumption (IW-NET project) for LL1	KPI	2-High priority
#07	Percentage of reusable/ recycled material	KPI	5-Not relevant
#08	The intensity of greenhouse gas emissions (kg CO2/km...) or Reduced environmental impact [CO2e] (GA)	KPI	2-High priority
#09	Habitat status	Dataset	Undefined (Specific to LL2)
#10	Indigenous and exogenous species status (Faunal and floral examinations)	Dataset	Undefined (Specific to LL2)
#11	Pollution rate (air, water, noise, soil)	KPI	1-Very high priority
#12	Water velocity	Dataset	2-High priority
#13	Erosion state (hydrological and morphological aspects)	KPI	Undefined (Specific to LL2)
#14	Sedimentation state (hydrological and morphological aspects)	KPI	Undefined (Specific to LL2)
#15	Fairway depth and width	Dataset	2-High priority
#16	Minimum bridge clearance	Dataset	2-High priority
#17	Water discharge	KPI	3-Medium priority
#18	Sedimentation (considering infrastructures)	KPI	Undefined (Specific to LL2)
#19	Sediment quantification (considering infrastructures)	KPI	Undefined (Specific to LL2)
#20	Erosion (considering infrastructures)	KPI	Undefined (Specific to LL2)
Economic and Environmental			
#21	ROI related to environmental protection	KPI	Undefined
#22	% of investments in environmental technology	KPI	4-Low priority
#23	Load capacity	Dataset	2-High priority
#24	Water level	Dataset	2-High priority
#25	Accommodation capacity for vessels (vessel facilities)	KPI	2-High priority
#26	Improved navigability capacity (GA)	KPI	2-High priority
#27	Increase in modal shift (GA)	Dataset	2-High priority
#28	Material fatigue (Based on life cycle)	KPI	3-Medium priority (Specific to LL4)
Resilience			
KPI defined in the GA			
#29	Reduce environmental impact (GA)	KPI	2-High priority

4.2 Economic Metrics and KPIs

To evaluate the economic performance of the IWT system, we will identify and quantify various metrics and KPIs that pertain to financial viability, cost-effectiveness, and overall economic resilience.

27 metrics related to economic aspects have been selected, they all relate to sustainability (see Table 4). The economic metrics undertaken are completely related to sustainability. They concern KPIs about cost and market share, water level, fairway status, ETA and loading capacities, some priorities are not set yet. These sustainability metrics may help us by referring to the ability to maintain the quality and reproducibility of natural resources and providing services in a responsible manner.

Table 4. List Economic Metrics and KPIs.

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level
Sustainability			
Economic			
#30	Total cost (transport, handling, waiting times, etc.)	KPI	Undefined
#31	Waiting time costs (in port or at a lock)	KPI	Undefined
#32	The total profit obtained in the transport	KPI	Undefined
#33	Transport cost (fuel consumption, staff costs, etc.)	KPI	Undefined
#34	Cost of cargo handling (loading and unloading)	KPI	Undefined
#35	State of Fairway engineering structures (availability, rehabilitation, maintenance, replacement)	Dataset	2-High priority
#36	Bridge clearance	Dataset	2-High priority
#37	State of floating marks	KPI	2-High priority
#38	Market share	KPI	4-Low priority
#39	ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival)	KPI	2-High priority
#40	Loading and unloading capacity	KPI	2-High priority
#41	Loading time	Dataset	3-Medium priority
#42	Storage capacity	Dataset	3-Medium priority
Economic and Environmental			
#43	ROI related to environmental protection	KPI	Undefined
#44	% of investments in environmental technology	KPI	4-Low priority
#45	% additional revenue (due to recycling etc.)	KPI	5-Not relevant
#46	Empty containers transported	KPI	5-Not relevant
#47	Load capacity	Dataset	2-High priority
#48	Water level	Dataset	2-High priority
#49	Accommodation capacity for vessels (vessel facilities)	KPI	2-High priority
#50	Improved navigability capacity (GA)	KPI	2-High priority
#51	Increase in modal shift (GA)	Dataset	2-High priority
#52	Material fatigue (Based on life cycle)	KPI	3-Medium priority
Economic and Social			

#53	Health and safety prevention costs	Dataset	4-Low priority
#54	Smooth functioning of passenger mobility (GA)	Dataset	2-High priority
#55	thresholds of pollution (air and water)	Dataset	2-High priority
#56	noise disturbance (well-being of neighbourhood and habitat)	Dataset	3-Medium priority

5 Models and Libraries

5.1 Models

A Digital Twin comprises multiple interconnected blocks or models that collectively replicate the real-world system, enabling a comprehensive understanding and analysis of its behavior. Figure 3 provides an overview of WP1's vision for the architecture of models and tools that could potentially form a DT for IWT. Each of these DT components serves a specific function in the objective of assessing the resilience of IWT, such as predicting weather, modeling hydrodynamic behavior, and simulating navigation and logistics, among other aspects.

Figure 3. WP1 vision of DT components. Source: IRTX.

Moreover, these models can exhibit differing degrees of sophistication based on their functionalities (see Figure 4). At the lower levels, there are models designed for data capture and visualization, serving to capture and represent reality. Situated above these are models integrated with metadata and statistics, which leverage real-time data to monitor the behavior of objects, processes, or services. In the higher echelons of ambition, one finds interactive models that empower users to conduct simulations and predictions through 'what-if' scenarios. Finally, there are active and learning models that harness all the capabilities to deliver interactive or autonomous recommendations to users.

Figure 4. Digital twin ambition levels defined in terms of the system’s capabilities (Michiels et al., 2023).

In order to compile the potential models that could constitute the ReNEW IWT DT, an extensive search has been conducted for the various models and tools from partners of WP1 and WP3. These models, either already in existence and set for further development, or expected to be developed during the course of the project, are listed in Table 5 and described in greater detail in the following subsections.

As seen in Table 5, each of these models serves different purposes, ranging from assessing the resilience of IWT with virtual models to predicting the cascading effects of threat and vulnerability scenarios, largely covering the functionalities of the components in the DT architecture depicted in Figure 3. Furthermore, each model is grounded in specific technology and exhibits varying levels of ambition, with a predominant presence of highly ambitious interactive models. It's worth noting that the scope of these models adequately addresses the requirements of each of the project's LLs.

Table 5. WP1 & WP3 models.

Model	Description	Ambition Level	Technology	Owner	Scope
M01. IWT Simulation	Virtual model to evaluate resilience in IW Transport	Interactive	AnyLogic	ITA	LL2
M02. Process Simulation	Virtual model to evaluate resilience in autonomous operations	Interactive	AnyLogic	ITA	LL1
M03. System Dynamics	Virtual model to evaluate innovation impact	Interactive	AnyLogic	ITA	LL4

M04. Bayesian Networks	Probabilistic model to assess the impact on resilience and sustainable KPIs	Responsive	Python or R library	RDS	LL1
M05. Bayesian Networks	Probabilistic model to assess the impact on the environmental variables	Monitoring	HUGIN	SINTEF	LL1
M06. Knowledge Graph	Graphical model to evaluate and predict the cascading effects of threat and vulnerability scenarios	Interactive	Protégé & Neo4j	VLTN	LL2
M07. Dynamic Routing	Multi-criteria dynamic route planning of the vessel fleet	Interactive	EuRIS routing based	IRTX	LL3

5.1.1 IWT Simulation

IWT Simulation is built on Agent-Based Simulation (ABS) technology. ABS is a versatile modeling technique used to simulate complex systems in various domains. It's grounded in the concept of representing individual agents or entities that have their own unique attributes, behaviors, and decision-making processes. These agents interact with one another within a dynamic environment, leading to emergent system behaviors. ABS is widely employed in fields such as economics, social sciences, ecology, and transportation to simulate and analyze scenarios with a multitude of interacting entities.

This model is specifically tailored for the IWT domain, with its agents representing the primary elements found in any IWT context:

- **Waterway:** geographic scope of the simulation represented by a graph of nodes and links with specific characteristics (water level, CEMT class...). Traffic rules can be applied to specific sections of the waterway network.
- **Port/Terminal:** these elements handle truck and vessel activities, with individual limitations on throughput and performance.
- **Lock:** locks have limited capacity and operate on a scheduling strategy based on typical lockage time distributions.
- **Transport services & vehicles:** vessels and trucks are responsible for the movement of cargo in the distribution network.

The model relies on input data to characterize each of its agents. A non-comprehensive list of input data includes:

- **GIS Data:** these data are instrumental for delineating the river's topological features, covering the network of nodes and links. They involve attributes such as water levels and other vital constraints within the modeling framework.
- **Infrastructure Data:** this category spans the characteristics of each infrastructure element. It goes beyond just pinpointing their location and extends to in-depth attributes. For instance, it intricately characterizes locks, accounting for dimensions, capacity, operational schedules, and processing times. Similarly, in the context of bridges, the model mandates data regarding their clearances or heights, essential for imposing navigational restrictions. Furthermore, valuable information pertaining to ports or terminals, including details on processing times, cargo handling capacity, and related specifics, strengthens the model's comprehensiveness.
- **Demand Data:** to capture the transportation demand, the model relies on data that typically quantifies it in terms of containers, pallets, or tons. This characterization also considers the origin and destination of the goods, allowing for a more holistic view of demand patterns.
- **Services data:** to simulate the transportation services facilitated by the vehicles operating within the network, the model necessitates data on routes, covering key elements such as origins, destinations, stopovers, as well as departure and arrival times. Furthermore, it is important to profile the vehicles, considering their speed, carrying capacity, dimensions, as well as factors including operational expenses and emission production rates.
- **AIS Data:** this dataset, comprised of ship movement information, plays a pivotal role in modeling. It aids in reconstructing the routes and voyages undertaken by vessels, enabling in-depth analyses and insights.

Figure 5. IWT Simulation applied to Douro River.

The model incorporates an interface (Figure 5) that provides real-time visualization during scenario execution. It displays the movements of different transport units operating within the transportation network on a map. Moreover, it dynamically presents various operational, economic, and environmental indicators, including metrics such as distance traveled, costs, emissions, delivery times, and more. The results from running diverse scenarios can be graphically analyzed directly within the interface or stored in structured tables for subsequent in-depth analysis.

The virtual model has been designed to provide answers to a variety of questions related to the IWT, such as:

- What is the carbon footprint associated with transporting a specific quantity of products from point A to point B?
- How does the choice between road and vessel transport impact the environmental footprint?
- What role does water level play in altering transportation durations and fuel consumption?
- To what extent can congestion at specific river points lead to delays in container deliveries?
- Which vessel type is the optimal choice for shippers looking to efficiently move larger quantities of containers between river ports on a monthly basis?

The model will be further customized as part of the ReNEW project to align and enhance its functionalities according to the specific needs of the LLs.

5.1.2 Process Simulation

Process Simulation is grounded in Discrete Event Simulation (DES) technology. DES is a modeling approach primarily used for analyzing processes that involve a sequence of discrete, well-defined events. It focuses on the order and timing of these events within a system. DES has broad applicability in a range of industries, including manufacturing, healthcare, logistics, and telecommunications. It's a valuable tool for optimizing processes, identifying bottlenecks, and evaluating system performance. DES models the flow of entities through a system and can help address questions related to resource utilization and capacity planning.

To initiate the construction of a DES model, it is crucial to establish a structured methodology. Business Process Modeling (BPM) principles play a significant role in this endeavor. BPM provides a framework for visualizing, analyzing, and optimizing processes within an organization. As illustrated in Figure 6, this modeling approach revolves around entities moving through a sequence of process blocks and events.

Figure 6. Example of a Business Process Diagram.

This framework can be adopted to develop a DES model by following these key steps:

- **Process Mapping:** Begin by mapping out the sequence of events and activities within the system being modeled. This step involves identifying the different components, their interactions, and the flow of entities through the system.
- **Event Specification:** In DES, events are pivotal moments in the modeled system, such as the arrival of a customer or the start of a manufacturing process. Each event should be clearly defined, specifying when it occurs, its attributes, and its effects on the system.
- **Resource Allocation:** Determine the resources required for each event or activity. Resources could include machines, personnel, or any other assets that play a role in the process. Understand the constraints and availability of these resources.
- **Time Management:** Precisely manage the timing of events and activities. DES models the passage of time, so defining event sequences and durations is essential for capturing the dynamics of the system.
- **Data Collection:** Gather the necessary data to populate the model. This data may include historical records, performance metrics, and any information needed to replicate the real-world system accurately.
- **Model Implementation:** Utilize specialized simulation software to construct the DES model, incorporating the information gathered during the previous steps. This will include defining the logic for events, resources, and the flow of entities.
- **Verification and Validation:** Carefully validate the model by comparing its behavior to real-world observations and data. Adjust and refine the model as needed to ensure it accurately represents the actual system.

- **Scenario Analysis:** Perform simulations with the model under various scenarios to analyze the system's performance. This can help in identifying bottlenecks, resource allocation issues, and areas for improvement.
- **Optimization:** Use the insights gained from simulations to optimize processes, improve resource allocation, and enhance system performance.

ITAINNOVA has extensive expertise in DES modeling of processes across a multitude of sectors. One potential application that could require the utilization of this model in LL1, an analysis of the impact of staff loss on the Smart Terminal, is described in section 7.2.1.

5.1.3 System Dynamics

This model is based on the technology of the same name, known as System Dynamics (SD). SD is a powerful methodology for modeling dynamic and complex systems. It emphasizes the interrelationships between variables and how they change over time. SD is widely used in fields like economics, ecology, public policy, and business management to understand the long-term behavior of systems. It excels at representing feedback loops, delays, and the causal relationships that influence system dynamics. This approach is instrumental in addressing questions related to policy analysis, strategic planning, and the impact of interventions in complex systems.

Within the framework of inland navigation, the literature has explored the use of dynamic system models for various purposes. For instance, a paper utilizes system dynamics models to evaluate and mitigate risks in the context of waterway transportation in mixed traffic environments. It delineates essential phases, models risk factors, and provides valuable insights into safety oversight, particularly concerning remotely operated vessels operating in these circumstances (Wan et al., 2023).

Also, government green subsidies in maritime supply chains, specifically for technologies like shore power (SP) are examined (Li et al., 2020). Authors use game theory to identify optimal subsidy levels and SD to assess real-world challenges. The study finds that shipper preferences and timing impact SP reliability, and it highlights the significance of addressing information asymmetry for downstream shipping line entities. A casual loop diagram of a SD model is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Causal loop diagram of SD model (Li et al., 2020).

Within the ReNEW project, a potential application in LL4 could require the utilization of SD models in order to conduct an analysis of the adoption of autonomous zero-emissions barges in inland navigation, which is described in section 7.2.4.

5.1.4 Bayesian Networks

Bayesian Networks (BNs) offer a graphical, multivariate approach that amalgamates data from various sources, including biophysical variables, statistical and deterministic models, and expert knowledge. This amalgamation enables the computation of event or scenario probabilities (Landuyt et al., 2013). More specifically, a BN is a directed, acyclic graph comprising nodes and connections between nodes, where nodes represent variables, and connections denote conditional dependencies. Due to their visual representation (Figure 8), BNs excel at uncovering causal relationships between variables. The graphical framework serves as a valuable tool for illustrating scenarios and engaging stakeholders in discussions (Pollino & Henderson, 2010).

Figure 8. Sample of a Bayesian Network model with associated CPTs.

Each node in a BN is associated with conditional probability tables (CPT). The input of each node relies on a set of values from the parent variable, while the output provides the probability distribution of the represented variable (Jensen, 2001). This probabilistic definition accommodates the inherent uncertainties found in natural systems and resource management (Pollino & Henderson, 2010). BNs have gained attention in environmental modeling due to their modular nature, capacity to handle uncertainties, ability to model highly complex systems, assess variable independence (Geiger et al., 1990), and bridge the gap between qualitative and quantitative modeling (Aguilera et al., 2011; Butz et al., 2017; Landuyt et al., 2015; Van der Biest et al., 2014).

BNs can be data-driven (Constantinou et al., 2016) and are versatile in handling diverse data types, including continuous data, categorical data, deterministic models, expert knowledge, and stakeholder opinions. They effectively account for varying degrees of uncertainty within this heterogeneous data (Aguilera et al., 2011; Landuyt et al., 2013).

The use of probabilistic networks like Bayesian Networks and Influence Diagrams (ID) as decision-making tools in water management has been demonstrated. (STEWART-KOSTER et al., 2010) harnessed BNs to prioritize flow and catchment restoration options, assessing their cost-effectiveness. (Barton et al., 2020) showcased how BNs can aid in decision-making regarding environmental design alternatives, such as environmental flow and physical mitigation measures. These authors recognize BNs' potential in handling uncertainties arising from data gaps and heterogeneous data sources.

Within the ReNEW project, RDS and SINTEF will use these probabilistic models in order to forecast the effects of extreme events respectively on traffic and infrastructure (RDS) and the ecosystem (SINTEF).

Below is an example of how BN can be applied to risk assessment. First, the hazard or events that constitute a threat must be identified/recognized/detected as well as their characteristics (e.g., occurrence, intensity etc.). Second, determining the impact of hazards, with high probability of occurrence, on critical and non-critical components of a system. Finally, the whole network's likelihood is measured without altering individual nodes.

The IWT network is illustrated in Figure 9 as a collection of systems (such as infrastructure, vessels, ports, etc.), subsystems (such as locks, bridges, etc.) and components (e.g., lock chamber, gate, etc.). Various data sources and expert opinions are used to evaluate the current state of the components. Damage metrics are assigned to each damage state, and these will be used to build CPTs. The BN model for risk assessment may then be created. A simple BN model used for risk assessment is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9. IWT network breakdown to systems, sub-systems, and components.

Figure 10. Simple BN model for risk assessment.

5.1.5 Knowledge Graphs

The IWT ontological framework

The IWT network is a sub-network of the intermodal transport infrastructure that interfaces through multiple IWT terminal nodes and river/ canal links used by a fleet of barges. Links are associated with river navigation parameters such as maximum barge size and draft for accessibility, speed restrictions in association with river flow/currents and water level and traffic data on locks and waterway segments. Node parameters capture intermodal infrastructure for loading/ unloading rate associated with road, rail and deep-sea cargo intermodal transfers. Locks, drawbridges and other IWT infrastructures are also considered as nodes with ‘accessibility constraint links to barge size/draft and mode of operation (first-come-first-served or on planned arrival).

The IWT features are represented on an ontology which acts as a formal representation of knowledge that captures a set of concepts within a domain, and the relationships between those concepts. However, an ontology for IWT is not limited to IWT infrastructure. A literature review of transport related ontologies carried out in ReNEW’s D1.4 (Rao & Connolly, 2023) has indicated that there are various components that require to be included in an ontology depending on the scope of the analysis, ranging from traffic management, to demand and user preferences, to environmental, policy and technological aspects.

The scope of the ontology extends to the analysis of IWT resilience and performance under disruption. It therefore considers a subset of performance indicators that extend beyond infrastructure modelling to environmental, social and sustainability aspects. As illustrated in Figure 11, there are several operational, infrastructural, and policy indicators that influence the resilience and responsiveness of the IWT.

Figure 11. Indicators influencing IWT resilience and responsiveness.

The top-level classes for the entities involved in the domain of inland waterways are as follows:

- Actions
- Hazards
- Identifiers/ Data
- Infrastructure
- Locations
- Measurements
- Operations
- Performance Indicators
- Personnel
- Port
- Propulsion System
- Regulation
- Sensors
- Vessel
- Waterway

These classes encompass the broad range of elements that interact within the complex system of inland waterways. They provide a structured framework for representing and analyzing the multifaceted components and activities within the system. This classification is based on the current understanding of the domain and aims to encapsulate the core aspects that define the functioning and characteristics of inland waterways. As our understanding of the system deepens and evolves,

these classes can be further specialized or restructured to better model the dynamics of the system. The ontology, with these top-level classes at its core, forms an essential tool for understanding, analyzing, and potentially predicting cascading effects within the intricate system of inland waterways (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Ontology and relationship key.

Probabilistic representation

A graphical representation of a BN is utilized to capture the ontology features of the IWT and the probabilistic relationships of its features. In its basic form a BN is a collection of nodes that represent objects, variables or elements in a system, and links that represent their relationships. Each node has a certain number of states representing the condition of each element of the infrastructure. The state of Node D is probabilistically dependent upon the state of node B, which in turn is also dependent on the state of node A.

Figure 13. Bayesian Network for calculating bridge failure (probabilities are omitted).

In order to illustrate the functionality of BN graphs further, a Bayesian network for evaluating the risk of bridge failure due to scour is illustrated in Figure 13 above. At the top of the graph are various properties of the river beneath the bridge (velocity, depth, discharge) as well as the bridge itself (abutment shape coefficient, skew coefficient). The state of each of these nodes impacts the following nodes, which indicate the probability of various states of local scour failure and contraction scour failure, at either a pier or abutment of the bridge.

In order to develop BNs for the ReNEW LLs, a semantic ontology is first required. Once this qualitative graph has been defined, local dynamics for each node are required. It is proposed that in the first instance, the graphs will be populated with probabilities based on expert knowledge determined through workshops with the LL participants. Various methods are available to optimise this process. It is proposed in ReNEW to adopt quantitative estimation through a framework which encourages feedback from experts, but also allows quantification of uncertainty. Subsequently, further workshops will be carried out in order to determine where more refined probabilistic models can be used based on monitoring and sensor data.

Decisions with uncertainty

The digitalization of the IW network will inevitably enable more disaggregate performance tracking in the network. At the same time there are several independent dynamic parameters influencing the performance of the IW network, such as hydraulicity (that determines the available draught for vessels) and bunker price or future green energy costs. To increase the competitiveness of the IW network and achieve resilience and substantiality, a decision support model that optimises the routing

and scheduling is anticipated. The ontological network developed aims to drive decision making under uncertainty for both infrastructure management and operational levels.

At an infrastructure level, the IWT ontology enables its operation as an integrated system with the aim of improving resilience and sustainability performance indicators. River operational and maintenance decisions are managed simultaneously aiming to improve the overall network performance. The probabilistic links between various network components in the Knowledge Graph enable the simultaneous deployment and exploitation of all IWT resources that lead to the identification of optimal management strategies.

Routing decisions are typically associated with barges, however, as federated logistics principles such as the Physical Internet are being deployed, routing decisions tend to become cargo specific. Uncertainty in routing arises from weather/ water flow conditions, as well as river management decisions. However, utilizing the probabilistic associations of the Knowledge Graph the two levels are considered simultaneously, enabling the identification of solutions that optimize both infrastructure management and operational aspects of the IWT network.

To achieve optimal performance, the decisions require to account for multiple externalities that spread beyond the IWT infrastructure, to the natural and build environment the system belongs to. Parameters such as pricing, demand, other transport modes, and externalities such as weather and water conditions as well as implementation and life-cycle factors of the equipment itself require to be considered. The Knowledge Graph enables their parametrization and formulation of a multi-objective optimization problem with an integrated utility function. The utility function accounts for the development and operational efficiency, resilience and sustainability that are modelled stochastically to account for the uncertainty associated with the system's externalities. The formulated mathematical program is set in a rolling time-horizon to inform both operational and maintenance decisions of the IWT and is solved using Monte Carlo simulation.

5.1.6 Dynamic Routing

In WP1 IRTX aims to develop a multi-objective decision support framework for the DT solution of the project. This framework will ensure the resilience and the sustainability of the inland waterways. These objectives are related to the KPIs that have been defined in Deliverable D1.8. A deep Pareto analysis of the elaborated mitigation strategies and alternatives will be done. As a first application of this framework, IRTX proposes to instantiate it on a common mitigation strategy that appears in most Living Lab Uses Cases which is the Dynamic routing of the vessels as a result of threat or vulnerability scenario.

For that purpose, different ways to achieve this will be investigated:

- Use the route planner of Euris¹ as a proxy calculator for a multi-criteria optimization inland waterways route planner by aggregating the different objectives in linear combination. Indeed, aggregation is certainly the easiest and most common way to handle multi-objective route planning problems with a single-objective optimization algorithm: a series of single-objective optimization problems are tackled in turn, the cost of each of these problems is defined by a linear combination of the objectives. For example, in the case of Co2 footprint and travel time objectives, both to be minimized, each linear combination can be defined by a single parameter α in $[0, 1]$.
- Adapt maritime route planners such as Halem² - Hydrodynamic Algorithm for Logistic Enhancement Module. Developed by TUDelft and is a route planner in dynamic currents. It considers spatial and temporal varying currents, minimal water depth and is able to perform an optimised plan according to the travel time, the travelled distance, the budget cost and the Co2 footprint emission.
- Other options could also be considered with the use of the internal planner of the 4shipping partner if the contractual conditions are fulfilled.

The multi-objective decision support framework could be generalized to all the mitigation actions and strategies once they are identified and mapped to the sustainable and resilience KPI.

5.2 Libraries

In this section, we focus on reviewing existing libraries, such as IW-NET and ICONET, with the objective of selecting the most appropriate ones to simulate resilience and sustainability scenarios in relation to IWT. These libraries serve as sources of prior knowledge that will aid in the definition and design of the Digital Twin Generic application.

5.2.1 ICONET

The ICONET project (Horizon 2020 Grant Nr. 769119) aimed to enhance the end-to-end flow of physical internet logistics through the creation of a new networked structure for interconnected logistics hubs integrated with IoT functionalities. It employed modeling and analysis methods, along with simulation, physical and digital prototyping, and real-world experimentation scenarios. By enabling the automatic routing of shipments to their ultimate destinations via an information-centric networking approach and by enhancing efficiency and customer service, the project aimed to contribute to the EU's sustainability goals.

A critical component of the project's modeling and simulation capability is the GPICS Framework (Ciprés, 2020). As illustrated in Figure 14, GPICS is defined through six interconnected aspects that

¹ EurIS - Route computation (eurisportal.eu).

² GitHub - TUDelft-CITG/halem: HALEM is a python package for optimizing shipping routes. This package provides an algorithm for optimizing the route for a given hydrodynamic model.

range from essential modeling components and base configuration rules (Modelling Kit) to the capabilities for defining/parameterizing scenarios (involving operational rules, business models, and collaboration strategies among various supply chain roles), including Master Datasets relevant to a specific EU geographic area. Additionally, GPICS incorporates a set of key performance benchmarks known as Baseline Key Performance Indicators to assess different PI scenarios, based on various combinations of configuration capabilities.

Figure 14. GPICS Framework.

The GPICS framework also serves as the foundation for simulation models. Elements within GPICS modeling and base configuration rules, found in the "Modeling Kit" dimension, directly correspond to simulation models. Modeling elements like hubs/nodes or corridors are represented as objects called 'Agents' in the simulation, and these 'Agents' exhibit behavior based on the fundamental configuration rules outlined in the GPICS framework and instantiated within GPICS definitions.

The GPICS modelling components are designed to allow the composition of a generic PI network through standard modelling elements. Through the appropriate configuration, these elements represent different types of supply chain flows. The structure of the generic model consists of the following main elements:

- **GPICS Container:** Unit load manipulated, stored, moved and routed through the systems and infrastructures of the Physical Internet.
- **GPICS Node/Hub:** Location specifically designed to carry out logistics and transport processes and activities on PI containers.
- **GPICS Transport:** Moving element used to carry PI containers through the PI nodes/hubs.
- **GPICS Corridor:** Connection between two PI Nodes/Hubs directly connected.
- **GPICS Route:** Set of GPICS corridors which connect a GPICS Node origin and a GPICS Node destination.
- **GPICS Network:** Set of containers, nodes, movers/transport, corridors, and routes.

- **GPICS Roles:** Actors/Agents involved in the operation of the PI Network.

Through the GPICS Framework, and with simulation libraries constructed from these elements, various simulations were conducted, encompassing a diverse range of scenarios such as synchronomodality services, warehousing and e-commerce fulfillment (Figure 15).

Figure 15. ICONET e-commerce fulfillment simulation.

The wealth of knowledge and expertise gained from this project, including the GPICS framework and the components of simulation libraries, remains readily accessible. It offers the potential for adaptation to create simulations specifically tailored to address resilience and sustainability scenarios. These simulations serve as invaluable tools for simulating, evaluating, and making evidence-based decisions across the strategic, tactical, and operational levels, particularly in the context of events related to the climate crisis.

5.2.2 IW-NET

The vision of the IW-NET project (Horizon 2020 Grant Nr. 861377) is to create an 'Innovation-driven Collaborative European Inland Waterways Transport Network' by following a holistic approach that not only covers digitalisation and multimodal integration in IWT but provides organisational and technological solutions for improved infrastructure management as well as for the next generation of green and innovative vessels.

As a result of the project, partners ITA and ISL have worked on simulation models for the inland waterway transport domain. This includes generic and specific requirements and conceptualizations,

a common taxonomy/ontology, as well as the implementation of models within the AnyLogic simulation environment.

The taxonomy/ontology defines characteristics and relationships between real objects or concepts (“classes”) within the IWT domain and may be used and adapted in further modelling approaches. In this way, a common understanding and wording is ensured which improves the comprehensiveness and integrability of simulation models (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. Example of common modelling ontology developed by ISL/ITA.

Building upon this ontology, a simulation library has been devised, grounded in various components specific to inland waterway transportation systems (Ciprés & López, 2022):

- **IW-NET Waterway:** This component delineates the geographical extent of the simulation, comprising a network of waterways or fairways that furnish crucial data and constraints for analyzing traffic flows. It comprises a series of fairway sections, each detailed with characteristics such as length and CEMT (European Conference of Ministers of Transport) classification. Furthermore, it accounts for section-specific attributes, including encounter regulations, navigability, and lock details.
- **IW-NET Port/Terminal:** Port elements encompass diverse processes encompassing the handling of trucks, trains, and vessels. These activities encompass tasks like mooring, loading, unloading, and even the management of push boats, complete with coupling and uncoupling procedures.
- **IW-NET Lock:** The lock modeling module takes into account various features such as predefined operating hours, processing durations, wait times, and split-locking procedures for push boats and lighters. Each lock employs an individual scheduling strategy, influenced by typical lockage time distributions for both upstream and downstream passages. Capacity limitations stem from the dimensions of the lock chambers and operating hours.

- **IW-NET Traffic Regulation:** Similar to the approach used in lock modeling, certain simulation scenarios necessitate the inclusion of local traffic regulations, which exert a significant influence on the scenarios. As demonstrated in the case of encounter traffic, specific segments of the waterway network can be modeled with reference to the relevant traffic rules.
- **IW-NET Transport Vehicles and Services:** These elements are responsible for executing transportation activities within the model. In the context of a synchromodal framework, they encompass vessels, barges, trains, trucks, and transporters that transport or handle containers within the distribution network.

Each of these elements is characterized by specific attributes or parameters. An example of attributes for a “Waterway” element is provided in Table 6. The complete set of parameters can be found in Deliverable D1.1 of the IW-NET project.

Table 6. Waterway element simulation attributes.

Waterway Attribute	Description
ID	Unique identifier
Source	ID of the start node
Target	ID of the end node
Bidirectional	Routing constraint for one-way sections
Geojson	Standard line-string used to display the exact course of fairway section and to calculate the length
Type	e.g., fairway, lock, canal
Location info	Text can be used to display additional information, e.g., the name of a river, lock or canal
CEMT class	The CEMT class indicates the maximum size of a vessel suitable for a particular waterway
Speed	Speed limit
Length	Length of the section
Regulation	Identifying the type of traffic regulation
Water level	The water level is expressed in cm and its calculation methodology depends on the country where the edge element is located on

An element in the context of the simulation model design represents a constituent with attributes like behavior, memory (history), timing, and interactions. The internal state and behavior of each element can be implemented in various ways, whether through a set of variables or by tracking the agent's status in a state graph. Behavior can broadly be categorized as passive (e.g., elements that respond only to incoming messages) or active, wherein the element's internal dynamics, including waiting times or system processes, drive its actions.

In the specific case of the library developed within the project, a combination of multi-agent and discrete event techniques has been employed to model these elements. Most often, these elements have been represented using state graphs (a visual representation of a system's behavior, showing

different states and how they transition based on events or actions). An illustrative example of a state graph used to model the behavior of a barge during a journey is depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Travelling behaviour state chart.

Furthermore, models to address specific problem areas have been developed. One concerns the investigation of IWT traffic flows along corridors which involve infrastructure bottlenecks (such as narrow fairway sections and locks) and thus are subject to different traffic management regimes (e.g., encounter restrictions, lock scheduling policies etc.). The purpose of using these models is to provide means to assess the impact of bottlenecks as well as the traffic management regimes. Potential customers can be found in the domain of strategic and tactical infrastructure planning. The focus is set on the “aggregated behaviour” of vessels, which is why the model does not reflect hydrographic effects and does not mimic vessel behaviour on a very microscopic level (e.g., reciprocal influence during certain manoeuvres).

Figure 18. Example of traffic flow simulation.

The model follows a combination of the agent-based and the discrete event approach and comes with a georeferenced network representation and routing capabilities. Input data generation and calibration of the model behaviour were done using historic AIS data analyses. Results can be obtained using a graphical user interface as well as spreadsheet-based output files (see Figure 18).

Another of these models focuses on evaluating various transportation strategies along the Danube River, comparing the environmental impact of conventional road transportation to optimized strategies predominantly utilizing inland waterways. This model (Figure 19) explores the effectiveness of different transport approaches and their influence on environmental indicators, serving as a valuable tool for assessing sustainable transportation options, particularly relevant for strategic and environmental planning.

Figure 19. Example of Inland Waterway Simulation.

6 Data Spaces

Data Spaces play a crucial role in our project as they enable the integration of heterogeneous data, which is essential for building a comprehensive and dynamic digital twin model. Through Data Spaces, we can achieve real-time data connectivity, efficient data management, and collaborative data analysis, thereby enhancing the accuracy and effectiveness of our digital twin.

By ensuring that our digital twin models are capable of integrating with Data Spaces effectively, we create a foundation for a highly interconnected and data-driven system. This integration enables the digital twin to harness the power of real-time data and diverse information sources, supporting accurate simulation, predictive capabilities, and informed decision-making in our Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application.

6.1 Data Sharing Requirements

The data sharing requirements within ReNEW transcend the requirements for operational logistics data sharing, where often two parties collaborate via point-to-point or hub-and-spoke integration. For example, within ReNEW we want to make data sources available for research purposes, for modelling and for scenario building within a digital twin context allowing for impact measurements on sustainability and resilience.

Data sharing within ReNEW is crucial but it comes with possible challenges:

- The integration with external data platforms may pose problems for those unfamiliar with them.
- Data owners may lack control over their data (data sovereignty).
- The data found may lack standardized metadata or vocabulary providers.
- The lack of trust between data owners/publishers and data users may hamper effective collaboration.

Data spaces offer a decentralized solution to address these challenges, bridging gaps between platforms and tools for more open data sharing (D3.1. Michiels et al., 2023).

Open Local Digital Twins (OLDTs) represent digital replicas of physical assets, systems, or environments, amalgamating data from diverse sources like sensors, IoT devices, and digital systems. They empower stakeholders to visualize, simulate, and enhance decision-making. Their success hinges on data and service quality from multiple parties, including local authorities, businesses, and citizens.

To tackle data sharing and collaboration challenges in OLDTs, data space principles can be leveraged:

- Discoverability: Vital for stakeholders to locate and access pertinent data and services. Data spaces facilitate metadata management and search functionality, enhancing discoverability and data exchange.
- Trust: Essential for confidence in data sharing and utilization. Data spaces establish trust relationships and enforce data governance and security policies.
- Interoperability: Ensures seamless data exchange across diverse systems and platforms. Data spaces offer standardized data models, interfaces, and protocols, reducing integration complexity and costs.
- Decentralized Identity & Access Management: Grants stakeholders' control over data and service access while safeguarding privacy. Data spaces provide secure authentication, authorization, and access rights delegation.
- Data Sovereignty: Ensures data owners retain control and monitor data usage compliance with legal and ethical standards. Data spaces enable tracking of data provenance, usage, and accountability.

Incorporating data space principles into OLDTs enhances collaboration, innovation, and value creation while safeguarding privacy, security, and compliance with legal and ethical norms.

Data can reach a digital twin and its components in various ways. The OLDT architecture avoids specifying data transfer protocols due to application-specific considerations. Notably, the data space architecture, as proposed by IDSA, features dataspace connectors. These connectors act as intermediaries between data users and publishers, facilitating pre-transfer negotiations and enabling shorter-lived sessions upon request, as depicted in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Data Space Connectors.

The comprehensive perspective pertains to end-to-end dataflows within the digital twin context. It is widely recognized that the principles of smart data must extend throughout the entire process to yield valuable solutions.

This entails the data provider adhering to all data governance principles and transparently publishing all facets of smart data through data space connectors. This encompasses not only technical data attributes but also quality, lineage, and related information.

6.2 Data Interactions within the Data Space

In the context of the digital twin, as illustrated in Figure 21, we can identify two fundamental types of data interaction.

Figure 21. Digital Twin data interactions.

6.2.1 Data Inputs

The first category of data interaction is associated with data input to the digital twin. This input encompasses a wide array of information sources, including sensor data, topological data, and more. These data inputs are essential components that empower the digital twin with real-time information, enabling it to replicate and understand the physical system it represents. Sensor data, for instance, provides critical insights into the current state and behavior of the physical entity, while topological data contributes to the spatial understanding of the system. The assimilation of such data equips the digital twin with the intelligence it requires to function effectively, offering a comprehensive

representation of the real-world system and supporting various analytical and decision-making processes.

Static Data

Within this category of data input to the digital twin, we can further delineate two distinct subcategories: static data and dynamic data. Static data encompasses information that remains relatively unchanging over time and includes details like the geographical location of infrastructure and the vessel registry. This static data forms the foundational knowledge that the digital twin relies on to understand the environment in which it operates. At the time of this report, the integration of the following sources is in progress:

- The European River Information System (EURIS) serves as an invaluable repository for data related to Europe's waterways, particularly its wealth of static information. This static data encompasses details about fixed infrastructures such as bridges, locks, ports, and other essential structures. Recognizing the significance of this foundational information for numerous stakeholders, EURIS offers connectors for the streamlined extraction of such data via its platform's APIs. By embedding these accurate and detailed structural descriptors, the developed digital twin will provide a reliable and fixed representation of the physical environment. This integration forms the bedrock upon which dynamic interactions and simulations can be built, ensuring that our digital twin remains rooted in the realities of Europe's waterway infrastructures.
- OpenStreetMap (OSM) stands as a global treasure trove of geographical and infrastructural data, offering a vast and continually updated repository of information about roads, buildings, waterways, and much more. Its open-source nature and the contributions of countless volunteers worldwide ensure that OSM captures a wide array of details often overlooked by other mapping platforms. For our digital twin, tapping into OSM becomes essential to extract complementary information that goes beyond the scope of EURIS. While EURIS provides specific static data on Europe's waterways and related infrastructures, OSM can fill in the gaps, offering data on surrounding road networks, urban layouts, landmarks, and other relevant geographical features. By integrating OSM data, our digital twin will gain a holistic view of the environment, ensuring a more detailed and interconnected virtual representation. Furthermore, the continuous updates from the OSM community mean that our digital twin can benefit from the most recent changes and developments in the landscape, ensuring its accuracy remains in sync with real-world alterations.

Dynamic Data

On the other hand, dynamic data comprises information that is subject to frequent updates and fluctuations. This type of data primarily consists of metrics that capture real-time conditions and operational parameters, such as water levels, weather conditions, vessel operational states, and other variables that can vary throughout the course of system operation. Dynamic data plays a crucial role

in providing the digital twin with the ability to adapt, respond, and make informed decisions based on the ever-changing conditions it monitors. By integrating both static and dynamic data, the digital twin maintains a comprehensive perspective of the physical system it replicates, fostering its ability to facilitate real-time analysis and support effective decision-making processes.

At the time of this report, the integration of the following sources is in progress:

- **EURIS' Dynamic Data:** The European River Information System (EURIS) provides invaluable real-time updates related to Europe's waterways, encompassing data on water flow rates, vessel movements, lock schedules, and more. This dynamic input ensures that the digital twin can react and predict based on immediate conditions, making it a real-time reflection of the current state of waterways.
- **Weather Service Providers:** Incorporating real-time meteorological updates from weather service providers enhances the digital twin's accuracy and responsiveness. Information on temperature, precipitation, wind patterns, and more allows the twin to anticipate disruptions, optimize operations based on current weather, and offer timely recommendations to stakeholders.
- **Water Level and Water Quality Sensors:** A critical aspect of waterway operations and management is understanding the water's depth and quality. By integrating sensors that monitor water levels, the digital twin can assess navigability, predict potential flooding or receding water levels, and optimize vessel movements. Concurrently, water quality sensors provide insights into parameters like pH levels, turbidity, dissolved oxygen, and presence of contaminants. This data not only informs about environmental health but can also influence decisions related to waterway usage, especially in scenarios where water quality is crucial, such as areas near freshwater intakes or protected ecological zones.
- **AIS Receivers:** The Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a pivotal tool for maritime safety and navigation. By integrating data from AIS receivers, the digital twin can access real-time information about ship positions, headings, speeds, and other vessel-specific details. This data is instrumental in monitoring vessel traffic, assessing congestion in ports or waterways, predicting potential collision scenarios, and optimizing route planning. Furthermore, AIS data aids in understanding vessel behaviors and trends, contributing to enhanced maritime situational awareness and operational efficiency.

6.2.2 Data Interfaces

A digital twin does not exist in isolation. In a complex ecosystem, it interacts with various actors, be it shippers, authorities, multimodal transport actors, or transport service providers. This interaction is twofold:

- **Acquiring Information:** Digital twins need to acquire data from these actors to have a comprehensive understanding of the environment. For instance, a digital twin for a shipment

might need data from transport providers about routes, schedules, and capacities or from authorities about regulatory constraints.

- **Providing Information:** Digital twins can also act as rich data sources. They can provide insights into the current state, predictions about future states, or recommendations based on simulations and analysis. Transport service providers, for example, might benefit from the insights of a digital twin in optimizing routes or maintenance schedules.

Given the myriad of interactions, standardizing data exchange becomes paramount. This is where the principles of data spaces come into play. By ensuring data sovereignty, secure data exchange, standardized interfaces, and clear usage rules, the challenges of data exchange in such a diverse ecosystem can be tackled effectively. It's not just about the seamless transfer of data, but also about ensuring that data is trustworthy, its integrity is maintained, and that all actors have clarity about how the data can be used. Incorporating the principles of data spaces into the digital twin ecosystem ensures a more robust, reliable, and efficient interaction among all involved entities. It promotes trust and facilitates cooperation, which are key in maximizing the potential benefits of digital twins.

6.3 Data Integration for Static, Real Time and Historic Data

This paragraph outlines the essential functionality required for data access and connectivity resources, which are instrumental in ensuring the seamless deployment and integration of DT technologies within the Living Labs. In this context, a virtual or digital environment is established, serving as a centralized repository and platform. This environment collects, integrates and process data from diverse sources associated with the use cases. The aggregated data becomes readily available for analysis, monitoring, and informed decision-making, facilitating various applications.

The dataspace for the digital twin is a complex mix of data coming from various sources, as highlighted earlier. The precision and reliability of this integrated data lay the foundation for an authentic digital representation of the real-world system. To achieve this, we categorize the integration into three distinct types:

- **Scheduled Replication:** Certain data sources are mirrored onto our platform based on predefined schedules. The ingested data, which can encompass a wide variety of parameters, is methodically stored within a time-series database. This approach ensures that the digital twin has consistent and periodic updates from these sources, allowing for tracking patterns and changes over time.
- **Advanced Interface Retrieval:** Some sources offer advanced interfaces, permitting on-demand access to both static and dynamic data. Whether it's real-time information or historical data, the retrieval process is designed to align closely with the dataspace concept. This means data is fetched directly from the source as and when needed, ensuring the most up-to-date and relevant information feeds into the digital twin.
- **On-Demand Data Requests:** For data that isn't frequently used but remains crucial for specific analyses or scenarios, an on-demand retrieval system is in place. Rather than storing this data

continuously, it's requested directly from the source when necessary. This approach ensures efficient use of storage and computational resources while guaranteeing access to vital data when required.

To manage this intricate web of data streams, a comprehensive registry of all data, their sources, and associated metadata is meticulously maintained. This is encapsulated within a knowledge graph, which functions akin to a data catalog. This graph not only offers a structured overview of the available data but also provides rich contextual insights, streamlining data discovery, understanding relationships, and enhancing the efficacy of the digital twin's operations.

Central to our data ingestion mechanism is the incorporation of the LDES (Linked Data Event Streams) specification. LDES provides a standardized approach to represent a series of time-ordered data events, particularly beneficial for systems that need to handle dynamic, real-time data. By adopting the LDES specification, we can efficiently capture, represent, and process changes or events in the data sources over time. In the context of our digital twin's dataspace, using LDES facilitates continuous synchronization with dynamic sources, ensuring that the digital twin always reflects the most recent state of the real-world system. Furthermore, with LDES, we achieve better compatibility with external systems and platforms that also adopt this specification, promoting interoperability and seamless data exchange.

7 Digital Twin LL Application

7.1 Methodology for LL Application

Imec and the ReNEW partners organised a set of workshops to get a better understanding of each Living Labs needs and innovation scope, employing imec’s methodology “Innovatrix”. The outcome of each workshop was the basis to further specify the solution concept’s requirements and the data and technology needs.

Innovatrix is imec’s own innovation methodology based on mapping and (in)validating innovation assumptions through specific innovation canvases. For ReNEW, the Smart Data Canvas was used via imec’s online tool (<https://imec.innovatrix.be>). For each Living Lab a session was held, where the responsible partners were asked to provide input. Imec moderated the sessions, while the other ReNEW partners were given the opportunity to attend and where necessary ask questions.

Innovatrix acts as a blueprint that transforms a use case into a set of assumptions, considering different aspects of the innovative idea. This approach helps us better understand the use case, and more specifically:

- its desirability - *for whom are we making it, and why?*
- its feasibility - *what will we create and how, what building blocks are crucial, and who could provide those to us?*
- its viability - *does the scope of the use case align with the goals and objectives of the GA and organization(s)?*

The Smart Data Canvas employs 9 criteria that we consider crucial for digital, data driven, innovations (see Figure 22). The approach is to reason from and compare the most important and relevant stakeholders for the use case. Doing so, we dive deeper into four crucial factors of innovation: focus, differentiation, coherence, and purpose.

Stakeholder			
Needs / Opportunities			
Current Practices			
Currents Datasets / Models			
Jobs-to-be-done			
Value Creation			
Key Resources			
Trustworthiness Requirements			
Barriers			

Figure 22. Innovatrix Smart Data Canvas.

During this stage of the project, we mainly focused on the ‘current state’ elements of the canvas –the assumptions regarding the current way of working (stakeholders, needs, current practices and data and models) while the ‘future state’ elements remained more high level, since more analysis was needed to specify the components of each Living Lab’s solution. Each Living Lab, and the ReNEW partners, were then encouraged to validate these assumptions, focusing on those that were critical for success.

Applying the innovatrix methodology early in the project, helped us – the consortium – to get a more consistent view of the Living Labs’s use cases and align on what had to be done. Moreover, it helped bring more scope and focus on the subsequent activities, identified (potential) conflicts or barriers early on and overall aided in informed decision-making regarding the next steps.

The output of the innovatrix exercise was used to converge the learnings about the problem and proposed solution into a definition of the solution concept. This was then translated into requirements and/or specifications such as Epics and User Stories, Architecture, Context Diagrams, the relevance in function of the KPIs, etc., that need to be collected within the DT.

After gaining a thorough understanding of the requirements of the LLs and the scope of innovation, the next step involves the design and the implementation of the DT, which requires a use cases

diagram representing the functional behaviour and expected capabilities which will serve as a guideline during the development phase. The Figure 23 illustrates a use case diagram associated with IWT-DT, as depicted in D1.8 (Tami et al., 2023). It gathers the main capacities that are expected from the DT to achieve resilience and sustainability in IWT despite climatic hazards and threats.

Figure 23. IWT Digital Twin use cases. Source: IRT SystemX.

As an illustrative example of a use case for the DT, Figure 24 showcases how users should be able to interact with the DT by configuring specific parameters to initiate simulations.

Figure 24. User-DT interaction to configure scenarios and run simulations. Source: IRT SystemX.

In the next section, we explore the potential evolution of the models presented in Chapter 5. Our objective is to provide an overview of how these models could adapt and find utility within each of the LLs. This exploration is essential to understand not only how these models can stay relevant but also how they can be tailored to meet the distinct requirements and challenges of each LL.

7.2 LL Simulation Models

As Figure 25 illustrates, the process of creating, developing, or evolving the models described in Chapter 5 is iterative. This approach starts with an initial design or prototype that rests on specific assumptions. However, as more information is gathered, encompassing pertinent data and the specific requirements of the LLs, additional constraints and features are introduced. These constraints serve to shape and fine-tune the models, gradually guiding them towards their ultimate version.

Figure 25. The iterative model building process (Robertson, 2002).

In this iterative process, feedback and close collaboration with users, experts and stakeholders from the LLs play a pivotal role. Their input and experiences help refine the models, ensuring they are precisely aligned with the actual needs and challenges encountered in the different LL contexts. The adaptability and continuous evolution of the models are essential for their effective application in the pursuit of resilience and sustainability in IWT.

In the following sub-sections, we will explore the initial conceptualizations of model applications within each of the LLs. These sub-sections are intended to offer an initial viewpoint on how these models can be effectively leveraged to meet the distinctive challenges and objectives of each LL.

7.2.1 LL1 Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchronomodality Resilient City Logistics Hub

In UC1 Smart Terminal, the impact of staff loss on the Smart Terminal or logistic operations will be addressed by simulation. The objective is to enable the Smart Terminal to continue functioning even in scenarios where personnel are disabled due to external calamities or pandemics. The approach undertaken will involve obtaining comprehensive information, data, and parameters pertaining to the terminal. A thorough assessment of the terminal's current state, including operational procedures, staff roles, and workflow dependencies, will be conducted to construct a baseline scenario as a reference point for analysis.

Subsequently, business processes within the terminal will be meticulously mapped using advanced techniques of business process modeling. This will enable the identification of key processes that are most susceptible to automation. Each process will be carefully analyzed to determine critical junctures where the transition from human-driven actions to machine-driven actions can be seamlessly integrated.

In addition, various variables influencing the terminal's processes will be identified. Factors such as workload fluctuations, external conditions, and resource availability will be considered to design a resilient and adaptive automated system.

Cutting-edge technologies that have the potential to enhance the terminal's overall performance will be explored. Technologies like Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Robotic Process Automation will be evaluated for their suitability in complementing human labor and maintaining efficient operations during staff loss scenarios.

Based on the gathered information, process mapping, and technology assessment, a comprehensive simulation model will be constructed. This model will be sensitive to the various factors and capable of simulating different scenarios of staff loss. The model will gauge the time element required for the seamless switchover from human-driven to machine-driven actions, a critical factor in ensuring uninterrupted terminal operations during personnel incapacitation.

Through analysis of the model under different scenarios, informed recommendations will be made, and optimal strategies proposed to the ReNEW project team. These recommendations will help in the formulation of a robust and efficient system that can dynamically adapt to unforeseen staff loss situations, ensuring the continuous functioning of the Smart Terminal and its logistic operations. By employing this proactive approach, this use case aims to fortify the terminal against potential disruptions and contribute to the advancement of automation in IWT.

7.2.2 LL2 Smart Douro Inland Waterway Infrastructure Resilience Management

Building a virtual model of the Douro River using multi-agent simulation techniques will provide a dynamic and comprehensive platform to model the intricate interactions within the IWT system. The simulation model will consist of a sophisticated network of agents, representing the key components of the river's ecosystem, including ports, locks, traffic regulations, demand, and various types of vessels. By encapsulating the complexities of the IWT system, the virtual model will allow for the exploration of a wide range of scenarios, unlocking valuable insights into the system's behavior under different conditions.

Safety and environmental protection will be at the forefront of the simulation model's considerations. By leveraging available hydrological and meteorological data, including real-time measurements of water levels and weather conditions, the model will enable what-if analyses during extreme weather events, such as floods. Such foresight will empower decision-makers to implement preemptive measures, safeguarding lives, property, and the environment along the Douro River.

Efficient navigation and smooth operations within the IWT system are paramount to prevent disruptions and avoid cascading effects. The model will intricately capture the detailed characteristics of locks, including their capacities, schedules, and passage times. This level of granularity will allow for the exploration of various traffic regulation strategies, where decision-

makers can enhance efficiency and minimize potential bottlenecks by considering key vessel characteristics, including but not limited to CEMT class, direction of travel (upstream/downstream), size, capacity, navigational features, and any other relevant properties, thereby streamlining operations and reducing potential bottlenecks.

Figure 26. Virtual Model of Douro River with water level representation.

One critical aspect that could be explored within the model is the river's connection to Leixões, a pivotal port within the TEN-T network. Understanding the impact of this connection and exploring scenarios where the Douro River can efficiently absorb increased demand will be instrumental in devising strategies to optimize freight flows and enhance regional trade.

The virtual model versatility and flexibility will enable stakeholders to test different scenarios, anticipate challenges, and devise proactive solutions. By incorporating real-time data and leveraging the power of multi-agent simulation, the model will serve as a decision support tool, empowering planners, authorities, and stakeholders to make informed choices and ensure the sustainable and resilient development of the Douro River's IWT system.

Ultimately, the digital twin will play a transformative role in optimizing the Douro River's transportation infrastructure. It will facilitate evidence-based decision-making, foster collaboration among various

stakeholders, and lay the foundation for a robust and efficient IWT system capable of withstanding future challenges and contributing to the region's economic growth and environmental sustainability.

7.2.3 LL3 Netherlands/EU IWT Network Resilience Mitigation DT App

According to initial design and implementation plans outlined in D4.12 (Kourouniotti et al., 2023), LL3 will introduce a Planning and Mitigation Module to the existing planning and scheduling platform, "Blue Wave.". This tool (see an example in Figure 27) will enable users to plan real-time inland waterway transport, even in the presence of disruptions.

Dynamic routing models, as described in section 5.1.6, could further enrich the tool. These models, supporting a multi-objective decision process, could ensure the resilience and the sustainability of the inland waterways when a threat or a vulnerability scenario occurs.

Figure 27. Route planner example. Source: D4.12.

7.2.4 LL4 Resilience Promoting Autonomous Zero-Emissions Barges

Evaluating the future adoption of a technology is a complex task that goes beyond simply forecasting technical feasibility or market potential. Technology adoption is influenced by a multitude of factors, each of which adds to the complexity of the evaluation process.

System dynamics is a powerful methodology for understanding the behavior of complex systems over time, making it an excellent tool for evaluating the adoption of autonomous inland water navigation.

The use of system dynamics provides a robust and flexible framework to assess the adoption of autonomous inland water navigation. It facilitates a better understanding of the dynamics involved, which can ultimately lead to more informed decision-making and strategic planning. System dynamics technology offers numerous benefits for such an analysis:

- **Holistic View:** System dynamics allows the examination of the entire system instead of focusing on individual components. This is particularly useful in autonomous inland water navigation where various elements such as technology, policy, economics, and environment interact with each other.
- **Understanding Complexity:** Autonomous inland water navigation involves many interrelated variables, including technological advancements, regulatory frameworks, user acceptance, infrastructure development, and environmental factors. System dynamics can capture these complex interactions and help us understand their combined effects.
- **Predictive Capability:** By incorporating feedback loops and time delays, system dynamics models can simulate future scenarios. This makes it possible to anticipate the rate of adoption of autonomous inland water navigation and the potential challenges and impacts.
- **Scenario Planning:** Through system dynamics, policymakers can test various scenarios and policies to promote autonomous navigation. The outcomes can reveal the most effective strategies to accelerate adoption and mitigate potential drawbacks.

In this use case, system dynamics models can be applied to analyse how the adoption of autonomous vessels in inland navigation can be evaluated. An initial prototype is shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28. System dynamics prototype model for assessing the adoption of autonomous navigation.

The following is a description of the main activities to develop this model.

- **State of the Art:** This task involves conducting a comprehensive literature review and analysis of the latest developments in the field of autonomous vessels and autonomous vehicles in general.
- **Design First Prototype:** Development of first functional prototype that includes the main variables and the initiating logic. This prototype is an initial version of the virtual model to test the functionality and to demonstrate to the partners what the overall objective of the model is.
- **Initial Workshop:** The first workshop is conducted with a group of trusted experts to identify the relationships within the model. In this workshop, the state of the art and the first prototype are presented, and the experts can criticise the model and give feedback to improve it.
- **Scenario definition:** This task consists of designing the group of conditions under which the model is to be evaluated, including the definition of scenario parameters, the context and the possible evolution of each of these variables in the future. Scenario analysis allows different future alternatives to be expected.
- **Data Collection Task Force:** This task includes the characterisation of necessary data that have been included in the model and scenarios. This involves identifying possible data sources or experts that can help characterise the dynamics of the model.
- **Validation workshop:** This involves organizing a workshop with experts or stakeholders to validate the model results. The team presents the outputs of the model, explaining the underlying assumptions, methodology, and findings. Participants, utilizing their expertise, will critically review and provide feedback on the presented results, thus ensuring that the model and its outcomes are robust, accurate, and reliable. The validation workshop is also an opportunity to gauge whether the model results are understandable and useful for the stakeholders.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable represents a step towards the Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin of the project. With the vision of a Digital Twin composed of multiple components (models and tools) that interact with each other, it was crucial to identify and describe these models.

To achieve this, we have compiled various models and tools from project partners. These models, which will be adjusted and evolved throughout the project, exhibit different levels of maturity or complexity, and are based on a wide range of technologies. Simulation models based on multi-agent technology, discrete events, or system dynamics have been identified. Additionally, bayesian network models, knowledge graphs, and even dynamic routing models have been described. These models constitute an initial version of the project's modeling and simulation capability, allowing us to address a wide range of needs, such as evaluating the resilience of inland waterway transport, autonomous processes and operations, or innovations targeted in the project, such as autonomous zero-emission barges. Moreover, these models enable us to forecast the impact and cascading effects of hazard and vulnerability scenarios by considering traffic, infrastructure, and ecological aspects, and to use these criteria to enhance planning through dynamic vessel routing.

Furthermore, we have gathered simulation libraries from previous projects, like IW-NET or ICONET, providing valuable insights into how to design resilience and sustainability models and scenarios for simulating, assessing, and making evidence-based decisions at strategic, tactical, and operational levels, particularly in response to climate crisis-related events.

To ensure that these models can be configured correctly and support the decision-making process of the Living Labs, data availability is essential. In this regard, we have introduced the concept of Data Spaces, which is the data platform that enables the integration of various data sources and their connection to the models. With this premise, we have introduced the requirements for sharing information, anticipated interactions between the Data Space and the Digital Twin and provided insights about how the information will be integrated.

Additionally, we have described the methodology used to identify potential Key Performance Indicators that help evaluate the capabilities of Inland Waterway Transport in two fundamental aspects: resilience and sustainability. Following this, we have compiled an exhaustive list of resilience, environmental, and economic indicators, all of which are particularly relevant to the needs of the Living Labs.

Finally, we have outlined the methodology employed to gather the requirements of the Living Labs and align them with the application of Digital Twin use cases. Subsequently, as a proof of concept, we have described the potential application possibilities offered by the models in each of the Living Labs. Over the coming months, we expect these models to evolve (and potentially new ones to emerge) as they incorporate data and feedback from users and stakeholders of the Living Labs.

9 References

- Aguilera, P. A., Fernández, A., Fernández, R., Rumí, R., & Salmerón, A. (2011). Bayesian networks in environmental modelling. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 26(12), 1376–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.06.004>
- Ahlgren, L. , & Jamac, H. (2023). *Staying Afloat Examining the Resilience of the European Inland Waterway Transportation Industry in the Face of Climate Related Disruptions: A Policy and Resilience Analysis* [Master 2-years]. University of Gothenburg.
- Ali, W. A., Roccotelli, M., & Fanti, M. P. (2022). Digital Twin in Intelligent Transportation Systems: a Review. *2022 8th International Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies (CoDIT)*, 576–581. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CoDIT55151.2022.9804017>
- Ambra, T., & Macharis, C. (2020). Agent-Based Digital Twins (ABM-Dt) In Sychromodal Transport and Logistics: the Fusion of Virtual and Pysical Spaces. *2020 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC)*, 159–169. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WSC48552.2020.9383955>
- Aritua, B., Cheng, L., van Liere, R., & de Leijer, H. (2021). Future Priorities for Inland Waterway Transport in China. In *Blue Routes for a New Era: Developing Inland Waterways Transportation in China* (pp. 99–120). The World Bank. https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-1584-3_ch5
- Azzi, H., Malek, H., & Sigronde, R. (2023a). *D3.8 Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v1 (ReNEW Project)*.
- Azzi, H., Malek, H., & Sigronde, R. (2023b). *D3.8 Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v1 (ReNEW Project)*.
- Barros, B. R. C. de, Carvalho, E. B. de, & Brasil Junior, A. C. P. (2022). Inland waterway transport and the 2030 agenda: Taxonomy of sustainability issues. *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, 8, 100462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2022.100462>
- Barton, D. N., Sundt, H., Bustos, A. A., Fjeldstad, H.-P., Hedger, R., Forseth, T., Berit Köhler, Aas, Ø., Alfredsen, K., & Madsen, A. L. (2020). Multi-criteria decision analysis in Bayesian networks - Diagnosing ecosystem service trade-offs in a hydropower regulated river. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 124, 104604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2019.104604>
- Behrends, S. (2012). The Significance of the Urban Context for the Sustainability Performance of Intermodal Road-rail Transport. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 54, 375–386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.757>
- Boschert, S., & Rosen, R. (2016). Digital Twin—The Simulation Aspect. In *Mechatronic Futures* (pp. 59–74). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-32156-1_5

- Brenner, B., & Hummel, V. (2017). Digital Twin as Enabler for an Innovative Digital Shopfloor Management System in the ESB Logistics Learning Factory at Reutlingen - University. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 9, 198–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2017.04.039>
- Browne, M., & Allen, J. (2011). Transport and Communications Bulletin for Asia and the Pacific ENHANCING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF URBAN FREIGHT TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS. *Transport and Communications Bulletin for Asia and the Pacific*, 1–19.
- Butz, C. J., Dos Santos, A. E., & Oliveira, J. S. (2017). On finding relevant variables in discrete Bayesian network inference. *The Thirtieth International Flairs Conference*.
- Ciprés, D. (2020). *D1.9 Generic PI Case Study and associated PI Hubs Plan Final (ICONET Project)*.
- Ciprés, D., & López, J. L. (2022). *D1.1 IWT modelling and simulation capability and Revenue Management methods for optimisation (IW-NET Project)*.
- Commission staff. (2021). *Towards future-proof inland waterway transport in Europe*.
- Constantinou, A. C., Fenton, N., & Neil, M. (2016). Integrating expert knowledge with data in Bayesian networks: Preserving data-driven expectations when the expert variables remain unobserved. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 56, 197–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2016.02.050>
- Diziain, D., Taniguchi, E., & Dablanc, L. (2014). Urban Logistics by Rail and Waterways in France and Japan. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 125, 159–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1464>
- Durajczyk, P., & Drop, N. (2021). Possibilities of Using Inland Navigation to Improve Efficiency of Urban and Interurban Freight Transport with the Use of the River Information Services (RIS) System—Case Study. *Energies*, 14(21), 7086. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14217086>
- Geiger, D., Verma, T., & Pearl, J. (1990). Identifying independence in bayesian networks. *Networks*, 20(5), 507–534. <https://doi.org/10.1002/net.3230200504>
- Goetz, A. R. (2010). The Geography of Transport Systems, Second Edition - By Jean-Paul Rodrigue, Claude Comtois, and Brian Slack. *Economic Geography*, 86(3), 321–322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1944-8287.2010.01075.x>
- Grieves, M., & Vickers, J. (2017). Digital Twin: Mitigating Unpredictable, Undesirable Emergent Behavior in Complex Systems. In *Transdisciplinary Perspectives on Complex Systems* (pp. 85–113). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-38756-7_4
- Jensen, F. V. (2001). Causal and Bayesian networks. *Bayesian Networks and Decision Graphs*, 3–34.
- Jović, M., & Duhme, W. (2023). *D1.1 Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v1 (ReNEW Project)*.

- Knapp, G. L., Mukherjee, T., Zuback, J. S., Wei, H. L., Palmer, T. A., De, A., & DebRoy, T. (2017). Building blocks for a digital twin of additive manufacturing. *Acta Materialia*, 135, 390–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2017.06.039>
- Kourouniotti, I., Hogetoorn, M., Burgess, A., & Snoei, J. (2023). *D4.12 LL3 Planning mitigation for climate resilient and sustainable transport infrastructure boosting modal shift Initial Design and Implementation Plans (ReNEW Project)*.
- Krause, S., Wurzler, L., Mørkrid, O. E., Fjørtoft, K., Psaraftis, H. N., Vilanova, M. R., Zis, T., Coelho, N. F., van Tatenhove, J., Raakjær, J., Kloch, K., Billesø, M. B., & Kristiansen, J. N. (2022). Development of an advanced, efficient and green intermodal system with autonomous inland and short sea shipping - AEGIS. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2311(1), 012031. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2311/1/012031>
- Landuyt, D., Broekx, S., D'hondt, R., Engelen, G., Aertsens, J., & Goethals, P. L. M. (2013). A review of Bayesian belief networks in ecosystem service modelling. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 46, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2013.03.011>
- Landuyt, D., Van der Biest, K., Broekx, S., Staes, J., Meire, P., & Goethals, P. L. M. (2015). A GIS plug-in for Bayesian belief networks: Towards a transparent software framework to assess and visualise uncertainties in ecosystem service mapping. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 71, 30–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2015.05.002>
- Li, X., Kuang, H., & Hu, Y. (2020). Using System Dynamics and Game Model to Estimate Optimal Subsidy in Shore Power Technology. *IEEE Access*, 8, 116310–116320. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3004183>
- Lybeck, T. (2019). *PROSPEROUS FUTURE OF INLAND WATERWAYS "INFUTURE" Project*.
- Maes, J., Sys, C., & Vanellander, T. (2015). *City Logistics by Water: Good Practices and Scope for Expansion* (pp. 413–437). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16133-4_21
- Michiels, P., Bergmans, T., Lefever, S., & Schrevens, B. (2023). *D3.1 Framework Architecture & core infrastructure components (ReNEW Project)*.
- Oztanriseven, F., & Nachtmann, H. (2020). Modeling dynamic behavior of navigable inland waterways. *Maritime Economics & Logistics*, 22(2), 173–195. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41278-019-00127-5>
- Pauwels, T., Kahle, M., & Brauner, T. (2021). *Market review on city freight distribution using inland waterways*. <https://www.powertechsystems.eu/>
- Pollino, C. A., & Henderson, C. (2010). Bayesian networks: A guide for their application in natural resource management and policy. *Landscape Logic, Technical Report*, 14, 48.

- Rao, R., & Connolly, L. (2023). *D1.4 IWT Infrastructure Resilience Interdependencies and Cascading Effects Knowledge Graphs v1 (ReNEW Project)*.
- Sari, N., & Patrick, M. (2022). *Second automated mooring system to West Harbour for faster, safer and cleaner operations*.
- Schleich, B., Anwer, N., Mathieu, L., & Wartzack, S. (2017). Shaping the digital twin for design and production engineering. *CIRP Annals*, 66(1), 141–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2017.04.040>
- Shafto, M., Rich, M. C., Glaessgen, D. E., Kemp, C., Lemoigne, J., & Wang, L. (2012). *Modeling, SiMulation, inforMation technology & ProceSSing roadMaP Technology Area 11*.
- STEWART-KOSTER, B., BUNN, S. E., MACKAY, S. J., POFF, N. L., NAIMAN, R. J., & LAKE, P. S. (2010). The use of Bayesian networks to guide investments in flow and catchment restoration for impaired river ecosystems. *Freshwater Biology*, 55(1), 243–260. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2427.2009.02219.x>
- Tami, R., Khouadjia, M., Asgari, F., Jović, M., & Duhme, W. (2023). *D1.8 ReNEW Methodology Specification for Resilience and Sustainability v1 (ReNEW Project)*.
- Uhlemann, T. H.-J., Schock, C., Lehmann, C., Freiberger, S., & Steinhilper, R. (2017). The Digital Twin: Demonstrating the Potential of Real Time Data Acquisition in Production Systems. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 9, 113–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2017.04.043>
- UNECE NEXUS. (2021). *Sustainable mobility and smart connectivity*. United Nations Publications.
- Van der Biest, K., D'Hondt, R., Jacobs, S., Landuyt, D., Staes, J., Goethals, P., & Meire, P. (2014). EBI: An index for delivery of ecosystem service bundles. *Ecological Indicators*, 37, 252–265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2013.04.006>
- Van Lier, T., & Macharis, C. (2011). Transport of goods to and from the center of Brussels: using the port to improve sustainability. *City Distribution and Urban Freight Transport: Multiple Perspectives*, 176–199.
- Vurdelja, J., & Vogrin, Z. (2005). Automotive fuel as an environmental factor. *Urban Transport*, 561–568. www.witpress.com,
- Wan, C., Zhao, Y., Zhang, D., & Fan, L. (2023). A system dynamics-based approach for risk analysis of waterway transportation in a mixed traffic environment. *Maritime Policy & Management*, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03088839.2023.2224328>
- Wang, M., Tan, Z., & Chen, J. (2023). Improving the resilience of the inland river transportation chain with flexible freight consolidation strategy under epidemic. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 243, 106757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106757>

- Wienk, T. (2021). *Evaluation of the resilience of inland waterway transport on the Rotterdam Wesseling corridor to increasing periods of low flow, following a Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathway approach*. TU Delft.
- Wu, J., Wang, X., Dang, Y., & Lv, Z. (2022). Digital twins and artificial intelligence in transportation infrastructure: Classification, application, and future research directions. *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, 101, 107983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2022.107983>
- Zheng, Y., Yang, S., & Cheng, H. (2019). An application framework of digital twin and its case study. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 10(3), 1141–1153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-018-0911-3>